

THE VERB PHRASE WITH A DEPENDENT COMPONENT EXPRESSED BY THE PRONOUN

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Abstract

It represents the structure of a word phrase English and Karaklpak verbal phrase components in personal pronouns in this article

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Phrase, verbal phrases, Dependent component, transitive verb, intransitive verb, personal pronoun in Modern English, examples

Introduction

The theory of phrase in our linguistics has a long tradition going back to the six century. According to our grammar and to Russian scholars the term "Phrase" can be applied only to such group of words which contain at least two minimal words forming grammatical unit, foreign scholars hold a different view of the problem of phrase. They consider that every combination of two or more words constitutes a unit which they term "Phrase" to combination to notional words and do not draw a destination between the two types of word groups such as " Good student" and " to the university".

It is known that a sentence is based on prediction and it consists in saying something about something, so that its purpose is communication. A phrase has no such aim.

One of the types of subordinate phrases is the verbal phrases. Verbal phrases are very important in syntactical structure of modern English. They are characterized with different using structural types, with combining create compound constructions.

Such structural variety verbal phrase must be classification into define types, without such division you cannot analyze those phrases consideration verbal phrases should be beginning with definition leading high, according to which you will be classification these phrases.

Classification of head verb (Head component) of phrase may be taken as a principle of classification verbal phrases generally accepted classification verbs into transitive and intransitive.

When Dependent Component is used in a transitive verb it may be called object component.

When Dependent Component is used in a intransitive verb it may be called qualifying component.

There are many types of verb phrases in English and Karakalpak languages. One of them is a verb phrase with personal pronoun as a dependent component.

This article is about the verbal phrases of which dependent component expressed by the personal pronoun in modern English and Karakalpak languages.

The English language has its own system of structural grouping and the signals of the phrase. The phrase is the combination of two or more words which is a grammatical unit but it is not an analytical form of some words.

The elements of a phrase may belong to any part of speech. A phrase most contains at least two notional words. Each component of a phrase can undergo grammatical changes in accordance with grammatical categories represented unit without destroying the identity of the phrase.

The complexity of the verb phrase is inherent not only in the intricate structure of its grammatical forms, but also in its various divisions, as well as in its falling into two different semantic forms as verb phrase with transitive verb and verb phrase with intransitive verb.

For example,

1. The Germans had inspected him closely. Nemisler oni abden kozden otkerdi (Transitive verb)
2. The delegation is going to Samarkand tomorrow. Delegaciya erten' Samarqandqa baradi (Intransitive verb)

The head component of a phrase can be distinguished from its dependent component because it determines many of the grammatical features of a phrase as a whole.

Verbal phrase can express various relations in the sentences. One of the them is a verbal phrase with the dependent component expressed by the personal pronoun by model " V+ P object " in modern English, In such cases head component of the use with the meaning

For example:

- a) To buy – satip aliw. Merchants bought them by weight. Sawdagerler olardi salmagi boyinsha satip aldi
- b) To catch – uslaw. So the Germans caught them. Solay etip Nemisler olardi uslap aldi

- c) To gather – jiynaw. She had gathered those together downstairs. Ol tomengi etajga olardi jayladi
- d) To keep – saqlaw. Because I can keep you safe. Sebebi, men seni qawipsiz saqlay alaman
- e) To call – shaqiriw. The next day he called me. Kelesi kuni ol meni shaqirdi
- f) To remember - eske saliw. She remembered him at dinner. Tuslik waqtinda ol oni eske aldi
- g) To know – biliw. She does not know me. Ol meni bilmeydi
- h) To understand – tusiniw. I understand you better. Men seni jaqsiraq tusinemen
- i) To forget – esten shigariw. They had forgotten me. Olar meni esten shigargan edi
- j) To see – koriw. I saw you this morning. Men sizdi bugin azanda korgen edim
- k) To respect – hurmetlew. I respect you very much. Men sizdi juda hurmetleymen

In our English examples all the dependent components of the phrase are in the objective case and the dependent components of phrase are given in accusative case in Karakalpak language

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